

Guidelines on Biochemical/Hematological Monitoring of COVID-19 Patients

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Abstract: Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) is responsible for the coronavirus disease in 2019 (COVID-19) which rapidly evolved from an outbreak in Wuhan, China into a pandemic that has resulted in over millions of infections and over hundreds of thousands of mortalities worldwide. Various coagulopathies have been reported in association with COVID-19, including disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC), sepsis-induced coagulopathy (SIC), local microthrombi, venous thromboembolism (VTE), arterial thrombotic complications, and thrombo-inflammation. There is a plethora of publications and conflicting data on hematological and hemostatic derangements in COVID-19 with some data suggesting the link to disease progress, severity and/or mortality. There is also growing evidence of potentially useful clinical biomarkers to predict COVID-19 progression and disease outcomes. Of those, a link between thrombocytopenia and COVID-19 severity or mortality was suggested. In this opinion report, we examine the published evidence of hematological and hemostatic laboratory derangements in COVID-19 and the interrelated SARS-CoV-2 induced inflammation.

Keywords: biochemistry; new coronary pneumonia; hematology; SARS-CoV-2.

1. INTRODUCTION

Along with the vital function for diagnosing excessive acute breathing syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) contamination and for assessing the presence and volume of an immune reaction in opposition to the virus, laboratory medication makes a vital contribution in the direction of chance stratification and tracking of inflamed patients. Whilst “routine” hematology and biochemistry assessments aren't unique sufficient to diagnose SARS-CoV-2 contamination, they play a function in several components of the coronavirus disorder 2019 (COVID-19) care pathway, along with affected person control and prognosis. This report through the Pathology and Clinical Laboratory Medicine on COVID-19 presents steering on: (A) scientific indicators for testing, (B) suggestions for check choice and interpretation, (C) issues in check interpretation, and (D) present day obstacles of biochemical/hematological tracking of COVID-19 patients.

2. MATERIAL AND METHOD

A. Role of the laboratory in the assessment of biochemical parameters in COVID-19 patients

Laboratory tests validated for SARS-CoV-2 are crucial for the timely management of COVID-19 because they support the clinical decision-making process for controlling infections and detecting asymptomatic cases. This expedites speedy isolation, adequate treatment and consequently reduces contagion rates.

Many laboratory parameters make it possible to assess the severity of the disease and predict the risk of it evolving toward more serious afflictions such as acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC) and multiple organ failure (MOF). Some parameters for which an unfavorable course of the disease has been described are absolute neutrophilia, thrombocytopenia, hypoalbuminemia, the elevation of liver enzymes, creatinine and nonspecific inflammatory markers such as C-reactive protein (CRP) and Interleukin 6 (IL-6). Notwithstanding the above, the main progression predictors described are lymphopenia, elevated D-dimer and hyperferritinemia, although it is also necessary to consider LDH, CPK and troponin in the marker panel.

B. Recommendations for check choice and interpretation

Many assessment articles and meta-analyses had been posted at the medical software of a few traditional laboratory assessments in SARS-CoV-2 contamination. These are summarized and mentioned below.

[B1] Key hematology assessments to screen COVID-19 sufferers

Leukocyte parameters

SARS-CoV-2 has been proven to have an instantaneous cytopathic harm on lymphocytes, with some of morphological modifications visible at the peripheral blood smear of inflamed sufferers [1]. Lymphopenia has grown to be a trademark of SARS-CoV-2 contamination and is gift to a variable quantity in nearly all symptomatic sufferers. There is likewise proof that the significance of lymphocyte counts discount friends with disorder severity [2].

A low eosinophil depend is some other ordinary marker of COVID-19 contamination [3]. The aggregate of lymphopenia and coffee eosinophil depend in a symptomatic affected person is a robust indicator of contamination [4].

An increased neutrophil depend has been discovered to usher in terrible diagnosis in COVID-19 contamination [3, 5].

Taken in aggregate with low lymphocyte depend, an increased neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR) may be used as a marker of unfavorable outcomes [6]

Markers of coagulopathy

A marked coagulopathy is a key characteristic of SARS-CoV-2 contamination. Coagulopathy maximum usually manifests as pro-thrombotic kingdom with expanded prevalence of each venous and arterial thrombosis [7, 8]. The mechanisms underlying this worry aren't completely understood, however are probable to contain a complicated interaction among inflammatory and pro-thrombotic factors, with endotheliitis and the formation of intravascular neutrophil extracellular traps gambling a vital role [9–11]. In addition, a subset of sufferers with excessive disorder increase disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC), with activation of the fibrinolytic pathway and intake of platelets and clotting factors [12, 13].

An increased D-dimer in inflamed sufferers has always been related to negative disorder development [3, 5, 14]. In addition, COVID-19-related coagulopathy may also gift with prolongation of prothrombin time (PT) and activated partial thromboplastin time (APTT) [12], and with an expanded fibrinogen attention, due to the robust pro-inflammatory kingdom [15]. Conversely, sufferers who increase DIC may also have a low fibrinogen attention and thrombocytopenia [7].

Thrombocytopenia is some other element that characterizes negative disorder development [16]. The low platelet depend is as a result of many convergent mechanisms, encompassing better platelet intake, lung harm with related megakaryocyte damage, drug-precipitated and immune thrombocytopenia, better platelet clearance, and decreased thrombopoietin manufacturing and bone marrow depression [17].

Table 1: Recommended hematological checks in sufferers with COVID-19 infection.

Test	Findings	Clinical utility
Complete blood count	↓Lymphocytes	– Lymphopenia is an indicator locating in symptomatic infection.
	↓Eosinophils	– Elevated neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio is related to bad medical outcomes.
	↑Neutrophils	
D-dimer	Increased	To become aware of the ones vulnerable to destructive outcome.

Platelets	Decreased	Associated with bad medical outcomes.
PT/APTT	Increased	To become aware of and screen coagulopathy
Fibrinogen	Increased/decreased	- Increased in COVID-related coagulopathy. -Decreased in DIC.

PT, prothrombin time; APTT, activated partial thromboplastin time; DIC, disseminated intravascular coagulation.

[B2] Key biochemical markers to reveal COVID-19 sufferers

Inflammatory markers

An exacerbated reaction of the immune system in COVID-19 patients provokes an inflammatory response called »cytokine storm«, which cause damage to different tissues contributing to worsening the condition of the patient . Lymphopenia and elevated proinflammatory cytokines have been reported to be frequent in severe cases of COVID-19 in comparison with milder cases, with higher serum concentrations of IL6, IL10, IL2 and IFN- γ present in severe cases [18, 19].

Therefore, the size of a few inflammatory biomarkers may be very essential for early and accurate identity of COVID-19 sufferers at better hazard of unfavorable development. C-reactive protein (CRP) is a typically measured nonspecific biomarker of inflammation. Increased CRP awareness has continually been proven to be related to terrible final results in SARS-CoV-2 contamination [3, 20, 21].

Erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) is an inflammatory marker which can be taken into consideration as an opportunity to CRP in resource-restrained environments, with a comparable dating visible among detrimental results in SARS-CoV-2 contamination and excessive biomarker values [22].

C-reactive protein is a plasma protein that is synthesized by the liver and induced by different inflammatory mediators such as IL-6. Despite being nonspecific, it is used clinically as a biomarker for different inflammatory complaints, and an increase in its levels is associated with greater severity of the disease [57]. In a study where the levels of C-reactive protein in COVID-19 patients were evaluated and categorized in four stages according to the computed tomography (CT) findings: initial (3 days), progression (7 days), peak (12 days) and recovery (16 days), the results of the seriously ill group (n=6) presented higher levels of CRP in the progression stage than the milder group (n=21), but decreased without statistically significant differences in the peak and recovery stages [58]. Moreover, Liu et al. [59] established that the C-reactive protein was significantly higher in the progression group than in the recovery/stabilization group (38.9 vs. 10.6 mg/L). In contrast, albumin diminished significantly in the progression group (41.27 g/L) in comparison with the recovery group (36.62 g/L) [60]. In the multivariate analysis both the albumin (Odds ratio, OR) 7.353, confidence interval (CI) 95%: 1.098-50.000; P level= 0.003) and CRP (OR, 10.530; CI95%: 1.224-34.701, P= 0.028) were risk factors for the progression of the disease. The plasma concentrations of these proteins in the acute phase (albumin, CRP) become modified by at least 25% in response to certain cytokines produced during different types of inflammatory processes where some degree of tissue damage is involved [61] [62].

Ferritin is a advantageous acute section protein, that's effortlessly measured and can be a marker of detrimental results in people inflamed with SARS-CoV-2 [23].

Procalcitonin can be useful in figuring out people with bacterial co-infections, who may also require precise antibiotic remedy and who've a worse prognosis [24].

Many extra inflammatory biomarkers had been studied and related to terrible final results in SARS-CoV-2 contamination. Examples encompass interleukin-6 (IL-6), interferon gamma-caused protein 10, monocyte chemotactic protein-three and presepsin [25–27]. However, for the reason that such biomarkers can't be effortlessly assayed in all laboratories and that proof is uncertain as to whether or not they upload any medical price past that already acquired thru size of greater widespread inflammatory markers, we'd now no longer presently suggest their ordinary size with inside the absence of similarly studies on medical utility.

Cardiovascular biomarkers in line with the proof that COVID-19 may also development to a systemic disease, cardiac involvement may also often broaden in sufferers with SARS-CoV-2 contamination due to direct cytopathic damage, cytokine-mediated damage, ischemia or maybe exacerbation of preexisting cardiac diseases [28, 29]. Several research has

proven that cardiac troponins are better in sufferers with greater intense illness, in comparison to people with milder disease [30–32]. The American College of Cardiology (ACC) factors out that accelerated cardiac troponins and NT-proBNP do not always recommend acute coronary syndrome or coronary heart failure and want to be interpreted within side the proper medical context and with the important thing offering functions of the affected person in mind [33]. An extended cardiac troponin in COVID-19 is probably to mirror an acute myocardial damage caused via way of means of both the virus or host immune response, in place of myocardial infarction because of rupture of an atherosclerotic plaque [28]. A meta-analysis of 4,189 patients in 28 studies established that seriously ill COVID-19 patients presented significantly higher levels of troponin, creatine kinase-MB (CK-MB), myoglobin and NT-proBNP. Acute cardiac injury (troponin elevation), was more frequent in patients with serious conditions in comparison with their milder counterparts. Predominantly, hsTnI and NT-proBNP levels increased during the course of the hospitalization solely in non-survivors [34].

Table 2: Recommended biochemical tests in patients with COVID-19 infection.

Test	Finding	Clinical utility
Arterial blood gas	Variable	To identify and monitor hypoxemia and metabolic acidosis associated with severe infection.
CRP	Increased	Associated with worse clinical outcome.
Ferritin	Increased	Associated with worse clinical outcome.
ESR	Increased	Alternative to CRP/ferritin in resourcelimited settings.
Procalcitonin	Increased	Associated with secondary bacterial infection.
Cardiac troponins	Increased	Associated with COVID-19- induced cardiac disease and poor prognosis.
ALT, bilirubin	Increased	To be monitored in patients treated with drugs known to affect liver function (e.g., lopinavir/ritonavir).
Albumin	Decreased	Reflects an acute inflammatory state and/or synthetic liver dysfunction.
Creatinine, urea (BUN)	Increased	Associated with poor prognosis.
LDH	Increased	Associated with worse clinical outcomes.
Interleukin-6, interferon gamma-induced protein 10, monocyte chemotactic protein-3, presepsin	Increased	For research use only. Associated with poor clinical outcomes (if validated assay clinically available).

CRP, C-reactive protein; ESR, erythrocyte sedimentation rate; ALT, alanine aminotransferase; BUN, blood urea nitrogen; LDH, lactate dehydrogenase.

Biomarkers of multisystem organ failure/damage

COVID-19 may be related to liver harm at some stage in disease

development and remedy, in sufferers without or with preexisting liver disease. Elevated values of aspartate aminotransferase (AST), alanine aminotransferase (ALT) and bilirubin, and coffee albumin and prealbumin concentrations have all been related to negative outcome [36–38] In addition, a few capsules used withinside the remedy

of COVID-19 are related to the improvement of accelerated liver biomarkers [39–41]. For this reason, at a minimum, it's miles endorsed to screen ALT, bilirubin and albumin at some stage in remedy of sufferers with hepatotoxic medications, and in people with pre-current liver disease.

Kidney harm is an extraordinarily common hassle in sufferers with COVID-19, mainly in people with extreme illness. Elevations of each serum creatinine and urea (blood urea nitrogen, BUN) were related to unfavorable medical outcome [3, 5].

Lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) is a non-particular marker of tissue damage. Probably due to the fact it's miles observed in lots of one of a kind tissues, LDH emerges as one of the maximum continuously accelerated markers in sufferers inflamed with COVID-19 at better hazard of growing destructive outcome [3, 5, 21].

[B3] Laboratory exams required in pediatric SARS-CoV-2 contamination

In comparison to adults, SARS-CoV-2 contamination in kids has a tendency to be relatively moderate. This statement is pondered with the aid of using the reality that, while present, laboratory abnormalities in inflamed kids are probably to be enormously much less excessive. Specifically, kids are much less probably to have atypical white blood mobileular parameters, however moderate elevations of inflammatory biomarkers (CRP, procalcitonin, IL-6) and D-dimer had been recognized in a few instances [45, 46]. There is a paucity of statistics concerning the correlation among biomarker attention and ailment severity in kids, even though it has been cautioned that a CRP take a look at end result above the cut-off can be related to radiological proof of pneumonia [46].

A small percentage of pediatric instances broaden a separate entity termed Multisystem Inflammatory Syndrome in Children (MIS-C). MIS-C is characterized with the aid of using a hyper-inflammatory kingdom progressing to excessive give up organ harm and more than one organ failure, that's subsequently now no longer so exclusive from the equal unfavorable inflammatory response found in a few adults. Elevated inflammatory biomarkers are taken into consideration to be a part of the diagnostic standards for MIS-C [47]. Laboratory abnormalities in kids with MIS-C greater intently constitute the ones visible in adults, with lymphopenia, and elevations of inflammatory biomarkers, D-dimer, cardiac troponin and natriuretic peptides being normally stated findings [45, 48, 49].

Recommendation [B3]: Laboratory exams required in pediatric SARS-CoV-2 contamination.

- Measurement of hematological and biochemical markers is not going to be indicated in asymptomatic kids.
- For people with scientific functions of contamination, size of a entire blood be counted number and inflammatory markers (e.g. CRP and/or ferritin) and D-dimer can be indicated.
- Given the not unusual place incidence of co-contamination with other bacterial pathogens in kids [56], procalcitonin size can also be warranted.

[B4] Role for scientific chance ratings withinside the prognosis or diagnosis of COVID-19

Given the affiliation among elevations in sure biomarkers and sickness severity, laboratory outcomes had been protected in some of scientific chance algorithms, evolved for

either diagnosing SARS-CoV-2 infection or identifying patients

at better chance of negative sickness progression [50–52]

The Corona-Score is a scientific chance rating meant to expect the opportunity of SARS-CoV-2 contamination in symptomatic sufferers imparting to emergency departments [52]. The rating encompasses eight parameters, 5 of which might be laboratory take a look at outcomes (absolute neutrophil count, absolute lymphocyte count, CRP, ferritin, LDH).

A Corona-rating

C. Test interpretation and barriers

[C1] Considerations for check interpretation

No unmarried biochemical or hematological check can confer ok records concerning the probably prognosis or final results of SARS-CoV-2 contamination. None of the assessments defined on this segment are unique for SARS-CoV-2 contamination or its ailment progression. Rather, the consequences of a collection of applicable assessments ought to be reviewed withinside the context of the patient's scientific presentation. Only on this manner can those biomarkers offer beneficial records withinside the scientific control of COVID-19.

It is critical to emphasise that a few variations among laboratory consequences in sufferers with intense and nonsevere ailment may be modest. For example, in a single metaanalysis, the weighted imply distinction in ALT consequences among non-intense and intense sufferers become handiest eight U/L [3].

This locating become despite the fact that statistically vast and has been replicated in different research. Based on those observations we advise that check consequences are intently scrutinised in view of the general scientific presentation, in order that the importance of small deviations from the reference c programming language or patient's baseline aren't misinterpreted.

Nevertheless, at the same time as maximum modifications will be modest in absolute terms, they may turn out to be greater significant for the duration of longitudinal tracking, for the reason that the intraindividual variability of scientific laboratory parameters is decrease than the inter-person version.

Recommendation [C1]: issues for check interpretation.

- No one checks ought to be taken into consideration in isolation. Groups of applicable assessments ought to be reviewed withinside the context of the patient's scientific presentation.
- Biological version of the analyte, and analytical version affecting check overall performance ought to be taken into consideration while deciphering intra-person modifications in consequences.

[C2] Current barriers of biochemical/ hematological tracking in COVID-19 sufferers

As COVID-19 is a brand new condition, there are ongoing demanding situations concerning the interpretation of literature findings to modern scientific practice. When writing those period in-between guidelines, we've got tried to consist of records replicated in more than one research to feature to the veracity of our recommendations. Nonetheless, maximum research referenced

In addition, a great deal of the posted studies does now no longer consist of records at the analytical techniques used for testing. For example, the extensive style of procedures used to degree and document D-dimer affords demanding situations while thinking about the anticipated modifications in D-dimer awareness in COVID-19 sufferers [55].

Recommendation [C2]: Current barriers of biochemical/hematological tracking in COVID-19 sufferers.

- We could urge warning while translating look at findings to neighborhood laboratory practice, specially while diagnostic cut-off are recommended

3. CONCLUSION

clinical laboratories play a pivotal role in the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic, not only from a diagnostic point of view but also in terms of the prognosis of COVID-19 patients, determining the degree of metabolic disorder of the patients and favoring the development of support tools for clinical decision making in order to adjust the therapy to the biological changes experienced by the subjects. Likewise, the laboratory work allows optimizing the hospital environment resources of the critical units of the health systems, resulting in the enhancement of the response time and efficiency of this response [63]. However, these approaches should be constantly reassessed based on new and reliable evidence published around the world, besides the incorporation of new technologies into the clinical laboratory work to obtain greater precision in the search for biochemical markers.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Singh A, Sood N, Narang V, Goyal A. Morphology of COVID- 19-affected cells in peripheral blood film. *BMJ Case Rep* 2020;13: e236117.
- [2] Huang I, Pranata R. Lymphopenia in severe coronavirus disease- 2019 (COVID-19): systematic review and meta-analysis. *J. Intensive Care* 2020; 8: 36.
- [3] Henry BM, De Oliveira MHS, Benoit S, Plebani M, Lippi G. Hematologic, biochemical and immune biomarker abnormalities associated with severe illness and mortality in coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19): a meta-analysis. *Clin Chem Lab Med* 2020; 58: 1021–8.
- [4] Zhang J, Dong X, Cao Y, Yuan Y, Yang Y, Yan Y, et al. Clinical characteristics of 140 patients infected with SARS-CoV-2 in Wuhan, China. *Eur J Allergy Clin Immunol* 2020; 75: 1730–41.
- [5] Bao J, Li C, Zhang K, Kang H, Chen W, Gu B. Comparative analysis of laboratory indexes of severe and non-severe patients infected with COVID-19. *Clin Chim Acta* 2020; 509: 180–94.
- [6] Lagunas-Rangel FA. Neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio and lymphocyte-to-C-reactive protein ratio in patients with severe coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19): a meta-analysis. *J Med Virol* Apr 3 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jmv.25819> [Epub ahead of print].
- [7] Becker RC. COVID-19 update: covid-19-associated coagulopathy. *J Thromb Thrombolysis* 2020; 50: 54–67.
- [8] Lippi G, Sanchis-Gomar F, Henry BM. COVID-19: unravelling the clinical progression of nature’s virtually perfect biological weapon. *Ann Transl Med* 2020; 8: 693.
- [9] Bikdeli B, Madhavan MV, Jimenez D, Chuich T, Dreyfus I, Driggin E, et al. COVID-19 and thrombotic or thromboembolic disease: implications for prevention, antithrombotic therapy, and followup: JACC state-of-the-art review. *J Am Coll Cardiol* 2020; 75: 2950–73.
- [10] Bikdeli B, Madhavan MV, Gupta A, Jimenez D, Burton JR, Der Nigoghossian C, et al. Pharmacological agents targeting thromboinflammation in COVID-19: review and implications for future research. *Thromb Haemost* 2020; 120: 1004–24.
- [11] Leppkes M, Knopf J, Naschberger E, Lindemann A, Singh J, Herrmann I, et al. Vascular occlusion by neutrophil extracellular traps in COVID-19. *EBio Med* 2020; 58: 10295.
- [12] Tang N, Li D, Wang X, Sun Z. Abnormal coagulation parameters are associated with poor prognosis in patients with novel coronavirus pneumonia. *J Thromb Haemost* 2020; 18: 1233–4.
- [13] Gando S, Fujishima S, Saitoh D, Shiraishi A, Yamakawa K, Kushimoto S, et al. The significance of disseminated intravascular coagulation on multiple organ dysfunction during the early stage of acute respiratory distress syndrome. *Thromb Res* 2020; 191: 15–21.
- [14] Lippi G, Favaloro EJ. D-dimer is associated with severity of coronavirus disease 2019: a pooled analysis. *Thromb Haemost* 2020; 120: 876–7.
- [15] Al-Samkari H, Karp Leaf RS, Dzik WH, Carlson JC, Fogerty AE, Waheed A, et al. COVID and coagulation: bleeding and thrombotic manifestations of SARS-CoV2 infection. *Blood* 2020; 136: 489–500.
- [16] Lippi G, Plebani M, Henry BM. Thrombocytopenia is associated with severe coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) infections: a meta-analysis. *Clin Chim Acta* 2020; 506: 145–8. 2014 Thompson et al.: IFCC Interim Guidelines on Biochemical/Hematological Monitoring of COVID-19 Patients
- [17] Zhang Y, Zeng X, Jiao Y, Li Z, Liu Q, Yang M, et al. Mechanisms involved in the development of thrombocytopenia in patients with COVID-19. *Thromb Res* 2020; 193: 110–5.
- [18] Mehta P, McAuley DF, Brown M, Sanchez E, Tattersall RS, Manson JJ. COVID-19: consider cytokine storm syndromes and immunosuppression. *Lancet* 2020; 395: 1033.
- [19] Ye Q, Wang B, Mao J. The pathogenesis and treatment of the ‘Cytokine Storm’ in COVID-19. *J Infect* 2020; 80: 607–13.

- [20] Yamada T, Wakabayashi M, Yamaji T, Chopra N, Mikami T, Miyashita H, et al. Value of leukocytosis and elevated C-reactive protein in predicting severe coronavirus 2019 (COVID-19): a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Clin Chim Acta* 2020; 509: 235–43.
- [21] Poggiali E, Zaino D, Immovilli P, Rovero L, Losi G, Dacrema A, et al. Lactate dehydrogenase and C-reactive protein as predictors of respiratory failure in COVID-19 patients. *Clin Chim Acta* 2020; 509: 135–8.
- [22] Lapić I, Rogić D, Plebani M, Plebani M. Erythrocyte sedimentation rate is associated with severe coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19): a pooled analysis. *Clin Chem Lab Med* 2020; 58: 1146–48.
- [23] Zeng F, Huang Y, Guo Y, Yin M, Chen X, Xiao L, et al. Association of inflammatory markers with the severity of COVID-19: a metaanalysis. *Int J Infect Dis* 2020; 96: 467–74.
- [24] Henry BM, Benoit SW, de Oliveira MHS, Hsieh WC, Benoit J, Ballout RA, et al. Laboratory abnormalities in children with mild and severe coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19): a pooled analysis and review. *Clin Biochem* 2020; 81: 1–8.
- [25] Zhu J, Pang J, Ji P, Zhong Z, Li H, Li B, et al. Elevated interleukin-6 is associated with severity of COVID-19: a meta-analysis. *J Med Virol* May 29 2020 <https://doi.org/10.1002/jmv.26085> [Epub ahead of print].
- [26] Yang Y, Shen C, Li J, Yuan J, Wei J, Huang F, et al. Plasma IP-10 and MCP-3 levels are highly associated with disease severity and predict the progression of COVID-19. *J Allergy Clin* 2020; 146: 119–27.
- [27] Zaninotto M, Mion MM, Cosma C, Rinaldi D, Plebani M. Presepsin in risk stratification of SARS-CoV-2 patients. *Clin Chim Acta* 2020; 507: 161–3.
- [28] Akhmerov A, Marbán E. COVID-19 and the heart. *Circ Res* 2020; 126: 1443–55.
- [29] Khan IH, Zahra SA, Zaim S, Harky A. At the heart of COVID-19. *J Card Surg* 2020; 35: 1287–94.
- [30] Lippi G, Lavie CJ, Sanchis-Gomar F. Cardiac troponin I in patients with coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19): evidence from a metaanalysis. *Prog Cardiovasc Dis* 2020; 63: 390–1.
- [31] Zhou F, Yu T, Du R, Fan G, Liu Y, Liu Z, et al. Clinical course and risk factors for mortality of adult inpatients with COVID-19 in Wuhan, China: a retrospective cohort study. *Lancet* 2020; 395: 1054–62.
- [32] Lala A, Johnson KW, Januzzi JL, Russak AJ, Paranjpe I, Richter F, et al. Prevalence and impact of myocardial injury in patients hospitalized with COVID-19 infection. *J Am Coll Cardiol* 2020; 76: 533–46.
- [33] American College of Cardiology. Heart Failure Biomarkers in COVID-19. Available from: <https://www.acc.org/latest-incardiology/articles/2020/07/27/09/25/heart-failurebiomarkers-in-covid-19> [Accessed Aug 2020].
- [34] Cai Q, Huang D, Yu H, Zhu Z, Xia Z, Su Y, Li Z, Zhou G, Gou J, Qu J, Sun Y, Liu Y, He Q, Chen J, Liu L, Xu L. COVID-19: Abnormal liver function tests. *J Hepatol.* 2020;73(3):566. doi: 10.1016/j.jhep.2020.04.006.
- [35] Guo T, Fan Y, Chen M, Wu X, Zhang L, He T, et al. Cardiovascular implications of fatal outcomes of patients with coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19). *JAMA Cardiol* 2020; 5: 1–8.
- [36] Mattiuzzi C, Lippi G. Serum prealbumin values predict the severity of coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19). *J Med Virol* May 29 2020 <https://doi.org/10.1002/jmv.26085> [Epub ahead of print].
- [37] Parohan M, Yaghoubi S, Seraji A. Liver injury is associated with severe coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) infection: a systematic review and meta-analysis of retrospective studies. *Hepatol Res* 2020; 50: 924–35.
- [38] Wang Y, Shi L, Wang Y, Yang H. An updated meta-analysis of AST and ALT levels and the mortality of COVID-19 patients. *Am J Emerg Med* 2020; S0735–6757:30426–5.
- [39] Cai Q, Huang D, Yu H, Zhu Z, Xia Z, Su Y, et al. COVID-19: abnormal liver function tests. *J Hepatol* 2020; 73: 566–74.
- [40] Bertolini A, van de Peppel IP, Bodewes FAJA, Moshage H, Fantin A, Farinati F, et al. Abnormal liver function tests in COVID-19 patients: relevance and potential pathogenesis. *Hepatology* Jul 23 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hep.31480> [Epub ahead of print].

- [41] Wong GLH, Wong VWS, Thompson A, Jia J, Hou J, Lesmana CRA, et al. Management of patients with liver derangement during the COVID-19 pandemic: an Asia-Pacific position statement. *Lancet Gastroenterol Hepatol* 2020; 5: 776–87.
- [42] Mojoli F, Mongodi S, Orlando A, Arisi E, Pozzi M, Civardi L, et al. Our recommendations for acute management of COVID-19. *Crit Care* 2020; 24: 207.
- [43] Tobin MJ. Basing respiratory management of COVID-19 on physiological principles. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med* 2020; 201: 1319–20.
- [44] Lippi G, South AM, Henry BM. Electrolyte imbalances in patients with severe coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19). *Ann Clin Biochem* 2020; 57: 262–5.
- [45] Hoang A, Chorath K, Moreira A, Evans M, Burmeister-Morton F, Burmeister F, et al. COVID-19 in 7780 pediatric patients: a systematic review. *EClinicalMedicine* 2020; 24: 100433.
- [46] Henry BM, Lippi G, Plebani M. Laboratory abnormalities in children with novel coronavirus disease 2019. *Clin Chem Lab Med* 2020; 58: 1135–38.
- [47] Centers for disease control multisystem inflammatory syndrome in children (MIS-C) associated with coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19). Preparedness E. Emergency preparedness and response multisystem inflammatory syndrome in children (MIS-C) associated with coronavirus disease 2019. Available from: <https://www.cdc.gov/mis-c/hcp/> [Accessed Aug 2020].
- [48] Feldstein LR, Rose EB, Horwitz SM, Collins JP, Newhams MM, Son MBF, et al. Multisystem inflammatory syndrome in U.S. Children and adolescents. *N Engl J Med* 2020; 383: 334–46.
- [49] Dufort EM, Koumans EH, Chow EJ, Rosenthal EM, Muse A, Rowlands J, et al. Multisystem inflammatory syndrome in children in New York state. *N Engl J Med* 2020; 383: 347–58.
- [50] Lippi G, Henry BM, Hoehn J, Benoit S, Benoit J. Validation of the Corona-Score for rapid identification of SARS-CoV-2 infections in patients seeking emergency department care in the United States. *Clin Chem Lab Med* 2020; 58: e311–e313.
- [51] Yang HS, Hou Y, Vasovic L V, Steel P, Chadburn A, Racine-Brzostek SE, et al. Routine laboratory blood tests predict SARS-CoV-2 infection using machine learning. *Clin Chem Aug 21 Thompson et al.: IFCC Interim Guidelines on Biochemical/Hematological Monitoring of COVID-19 Patients 20152020*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/clinchem/hvaa200> [Epub ahead of print].
- [52] Kurstjens S, van der Horst A, Herpers R, Geerits MWL, Kluiters-de Hingh YCM, Göttgens E-L, et al. Rapid identification of SARS-CoV-2-infected patients at the emergency department using routine testing. *Clin Chem Lab Med Jun 29 2020*. <https://doi.org/10.1515/cclm-2020-059310.1101/2020.04.20.20067512> [Epub ahead of print].
- [53] Liang W, Liang H, Ou L, Chen B, Chen A, Li C, et al. Development and validation of a clinical risk score to predict the occurrence of critical illness in hospitalized patients with COVID-19. *JAMA Intern Med* 2020; 180: 1–9.
- [54] Wynants L, Van Calster B, Bonten MMJ, Collins GS, Debray TPA, De Vos M, et al. Prediction models for diagnosis and prognosis of covid-19 infection: Systematic review and critical appraisal. *BMJ Apr 7 2020*. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.m1328> [Epub ahead of print].
- [55] Favaloro EJ, Thachil J. Reporting of D-dimer data in COVID-19: some confusion and potential for misinformation. *Clin Chem Lab Med* 2020; 58: 1191–99.
- [56] Wu Q, Xing Y, Shi L, Li W, Gao Y, Pan S, et al. Coinfection and other clinical characteristics of COVID-19 in children. *Pediatrics. Am Acad Pediatr Jul 2020* <https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2020-0961> [Epub ahead of print].
- [57] Gong J, Dong H, Xia Q, Huang Z, Wang D, Zhao Y, Liu W, Tu S, Zhang M, Wang Q, Lu F. *Correlation analysis between disease severity and inflammation-related parameters in patients with COVID-19 pneumonia*. Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory; 2020.
- [58] Ahnach M, Zbiri S, Nejari S, Ousti F, Elkettani C. C-reactive protein as an early predictor of COVID-19 severity. *J Med Biochem*. 2020;39(4):500. doi: 10.5937/jomb0-27554.

- [59] Tan C, Huang Y, Shi F, Tan K, Ma Q, Chen Y, Jiang X, Li X. C-reactive protein correlates with computed tomographic findings and predicts severe COVID-19 early. *J Med Virol.* 2020;92(7):856. doi: 10.1002/jmv.25871.
- [60] Hu Y, Yang M, Liu H, Liu J, Deng Y, Wei S, Zhou L, Liu K, Yuan M L, Wang L, Tao Z W, Liu W. Analysis of factors associated with disease outcomes in hospitalized patients with 2019 novel coronavirus disease. *Chin Med J (Engl)* 2020;133(9):1032. doi: 10.1097/cm9.0000000000000775.
- [61] Pepys M B, Hirschfield G M. C-reactive protein: A critical update. *J Clin Invest.* 2003;111(12):1805. doi: 10.1172/jci200318921.
- [62] Kinoshita A, Onoda H, Imai N, Iwaku A, Oishi M, Tanaka K, Fushiya N, Koike K, Nishino H, Matsushima M. The C-reactive protein/albumin ratio, a novel inflammation-based prognostic score, predicts outcomes in patients with hepatocellular carcinoma. *Ann Surg Oncol.* 2015;22(3):803. doi: 10.1245/s10434-014-4048-0.
- [63] Lippi G, Plebani M. The critical role of laboratory medicine during coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) and other viral outbreaks. *Clin Chem Lab Med.* 2020;58(7):1063. doi: 10.1515/cclm-2020-0240.